

Community Collaboration and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Community collaboration has a link with teachers' job performance. Hence this study investigated how community collaboration contributes to teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Delta State. Two research questions, and hypotheses guided the study. A correlational research design was used for the study, with a population of 489 principals in public secondary schools in Delta State. A sample size of 98 respondents was derived using multi stage sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaire titled community collaboration questionnaire (CCQ) and teachers' job performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) was used for the study. The reliability index of the instrument was 0.89 using the Cronbach Alpha method. Simple regression was used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. Findings showed, that effective communication through community collaboration contributes highly to teachers' job performance and there was a significant contribution between effective communication through community collaboration and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta State. The study concluded that community collaboration contributes to teachers' job performance hence there should be room for community to be fully involved in the activities of the schools in Delta State. The study recommended, among others, that the principals should give room for community collaboration so that the community members can increase their participation in school management.

Keywords: Community, Collaboration, Teachers, Performance

Introduction

The community is a social system which has an unrestricted geographical area and it can be a state, local school or an area served by a school. The school relies on its community entity for almost everything it needs in terms of teaching and non-teaching staff, students, facilities, funds and other resources. Every school is found in a community; therefore, no school is situated on an island (Epstein, 2022). Hence, no school exists in isolation of the community. Schools are sited in communities and are sometimes metaphorically referred to as islands with no bridges to the mainland. The community can also be seen as a residential or geographical area whose inhabitants share common ideas, customs, traditions, beliefs and patterns of behaviour. In as much as the school cannot live without support from the community, it also cannot exist without teachers. The teaching force in the school determines the quality of education delivered by the school since no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers. The teacher is seen as a person who thinks positively and works hard to ensure that the aims and objectives of education are achieved by transferring knowledge to students and making them knowledgeable in all aspects (Moses-Promise & Moses, 2016; Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). Performance can be seen as a means of achieving or doing a particular task. Moses-Promise and Ayamele (2018) posited that teachers' performance is to a great extent dependent on teachers' characteristics (knowledge, sense of responsibility and inquisitiveness); student characteristics (opportunity to learn and academic work); teaching factors (lesson structure and communication); learning aspects (involvement and success) and classroom phenomena (environment, climate, organization and management). Recent studies also show that effective teacher performance is influenced by collaboration, professional support and community involvement in school activities (OECD, 2021; Kraft & Falken, 2021). In other words, the teacher's job will not be complete without community collaboration.

Community collaboration deals with individuals in an organization being able to work together in achieving a common goal that benefits the entire community. Community collaboration can be defined as the symbiotic relationship existing between the school and the community (Alabi et al., 2022). It is also a two-way process between the community and the school because they both cannot do without each other. Thus, teachers and schools must work hand in hand with the community to

achieve educational goals. Studies have indicated that effective school–community partnership enhances teachers’ effectiveness, improves students’ learning outcomes and strengthens the educational system (Hill & Torres, 2020; Epstein, 2022). As long as the school is situated in a community, it is responsible for transmitting culture, beliefs and attitudes to its recipients. The most important position in the school system is occupied by the school.

A community can be defined as a geographical area being occupied by a group of people with same culture, beliefs, values, traditions and a common interest. as a group of people living in a geographical area, who have identical culture, beliefs, values, traditions and are united with common interest. They share a common territory because of the common interest that brings them together. A community can also be defined as a social group that has occupied a defined geographical area based on how they feel for each other (Ewelenu & Mbara, 2016). There are three types of communities according to Baiz (2013) which includes the geographic community, which is defined according to its members’ place of residence, such as a village or district, ethnic, racial and religious communities, in which membership is based on ethnic, racial, or religious identification and commonly cuts across membership based on geographic location while the last one is based on shared family or educational concerns, which include parents associations and similar bodies that are based on families’ shared concern for the welfare of students.

According to Mohammed, et al., (2015), there are five ways a community can collaborate with the school to ensure teachers’ job performance and students’ performance also. They include enrolment of school age children to school prepared to learn; provision of financial and material support to the school; effective communication between the school, parents, and community; community’s role in school administration and community’s participation and assistance with instruction. In other words when the community is in collaboration with the school, teachers’ performance will increase in the following ways: there will efficiency participation which means that the chances that the available resources for project development will be adequately used. The rate of misunderstanding and disagreements between the school and community will be minimal because time and energy will be saved in terms of trying to convince people on the benefits of project development. Collaboration also reduces cost because in executing a project, some persons and resources from the community will be

used thereby reducing the number of professionals that will be employed for a project (Ojibara, 2002).

Teachers' job performance can be enhanced through community collaboration if there is effective communication and adequate resource sharing. Communication is an indispensable management tool in every organization and the school is not an exemption. It has to do with the transfer of ideas, feelings, insights, facts, attitudes or intents to others for the purpose of influencing their behaviours (Udeozor, 2005). Communication also involves the means of sharing information and understanding from one person to another and it can only be said to be effective wherever it is used and when the purpose for which it took place is achieved that is when the message that is been passed across gets to the receiver and it is well understood and interpreted by the receiver. In terms of community collaboration, communication is very important because it minimizes conflicts between the school and the community thereby leading to improved teachers' job performance. Effective communication between the school and the community includes clarity of ideas before communicating, careful examination of the purpose of communication, understanding the physical and human environment, consulting others to obtain their views before planning communication, carefully considering the context of the message, communicating only valued information by the receiver, do a follow-up to the messages that are of short and long run importance, making action congruent with communication (Obi, 2002).

Resource sharing on the other hand is the process of distributing and allocating resources among multiple users or systems so as to optimize their efficiency. It helps the community in order to strengthen school programmes, family practices, and student teaching (Stephen, 2014). Community participation in resource sharing therefore is the creation of opportunities to enable all members of a community and the larger society to actively contribute to and influence in the development process and to share equitably in the fruits of development (Shilpi, 2017). In other words, resource sharing helps teachers by broadening their access to tools and support thereby enhancing their professional growth and improving the overall educational experience for their students. Therefore if these resources are to be shared between the school and the community, then they should also both manage the resources. Hence, resource management is the practice of planning, scheduling, and allocating

people, money, and technology to a project or program. In essence, it is the process of allocating resources to achieve organizational goals. Good resource management results in the right resources being available at the right time for the right work and by so doing, teachers' job performance will be improved. Transparency is the key to effective resource management giving project managers insight into all resources and where they are allocated across projects (Townsend, 2023).

Statement of the Problem

The quality of school community relations is increasingly becoming a priority concern to stakeholders in the education industry globally. In Nigeria, the quest is about the same as the issue of effective school relations has become fundamental and always recurring in educational discourse due to the linkage between the school environment with regard to the host community and teachers' performance. Indeed, the quality of school community relations is increasingly becoming a priority concern to stakeholders in the education industry globally. In Delta State, the quest is about the same as the issue of effective school relations has become fundamental and always recurring in educational discourse due to the linkage between the school environment with regard to the host community and teachers' performance. From observation, most schools are in conflict with their communities and vice versa because of lack of communication and resource sharing. Hence this study tends to investigate if actually community collaboration contributes to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study

1. how does effective communication through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state?
2. how does resource sharing through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state?

Hypotheses

H₀₁: there is no significant contribution to effective communication through community collaboration of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.

Ho2: there is no significant contribution to resource sharing through community collaboration of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.

Purpose of the Study

The study sought to:

1. ascertain how effective communication through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.
2. examine how resource sharing through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this study was the attribution theory propounded by Fritz Heider (1958). This theory according to Kpee (2015), contended that behaviour can be accounted for by personal forces and environmental forces. These personal forces are referred to as the individuals' ability and effort and these could be internal or within the individual and these environmental forces consist of the things found outside the individual or within his habitation that can persuade him to behave the way he does. In other words, the behavior of the individual is attributed to both the personal and environmental forces. Kpee (2015) in applying this theory to education says how the individuals manage themselves and the environment which they find themselves so as to attain set goals. This theory is of great importance to this work because it is related to the school administrators. Teachers' performance will be enhanced if there is a peaceful community collaboration between the school and the community.

Methodology

The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of this study consisted of four hundred and eighty-nine (489) principals from 489 public secondary schools in Delta State. The sample of 98 principals was drawn representing 20% of the population using the multi stage sampling technique method. A questionnaire designed by the researcher, titled community collaboration questionnaire (CCQ) and teachers' job performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)," was used to gather data.

The reliability of the instrument was tested using the Cronbach Alpha method and the reliability index was 0.89. Simple regression was used to answer the research question while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Research Question One: How does effective communication through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state?

Table 1: Simple regression analysis on how effective communication through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta State.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard error of the estimate
1	0.470	0.940	0.531	2.85

Table 1 showed how effective communication through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance with 0.940. Therefore, effective communication through community collaboration contributes highly to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta State.

Research Question Two: How does resource sharing through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state?

Table 2: Simple regression analysis on how resource sharing through community collaboration contribute to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta State.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard error of the estimate
1	0.302	0.604	0.619	3.56

Table 2 showed how resource sharing through community collaboration contribute to teachers’ job performance with 0.604. Therefore, resource sharing through community collaboration contributes moderately to teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Delta State.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant contribution of effective communication through community collaboration to teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.

Table 3: t-test associated with simple regression analysis on how effective communication through community collaboration contributes to teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	31.754	3.253		11.843	
Effective communication	0.374	0.069	0.447	4.751	0.012

Table 3 showed the probability value to be 0.012 which is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence there was a significant contribution of effective communication through community collaboration to teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Delta state. In other words, we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant contribution of resource sharing through community collaboration to teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.

Table 4: t-test associated with simple regression analysis on how resource sharing through community collaboration contributes to teachers’ job performance in secondary schools in Delta state.

	Unstandardized coefficients	Standardized coefficients	T

Model	B	Std. Error	Beta		Sig.
(Constant)	61.121	2.532		30.401	
Resource sharing	0.045	0.078	0.072	0.337	0.730

Table 4 showed the probability value to be 0.730 which is higher than the significant level of 0.05. Hence there was no significant contribution of resource sharing through community collaboration to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state. Based on the above, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated how community collaboration contributes to teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta State. However, findings of the study showed that effective communication through community collaboration contributes highly to teachers' job performance and there was a significant contribution between effective communication through community collaboration and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state. The findings from this study are corroborated by Udeozor (2005) who revealed that communication is an indispensable management tool in every organization and it will enhance school community collaboration. Findings from the study also showed that the resource sharing through community collaboration contributes moderately to teachers' job performance and there was no significant contribution between resource sharing through community collaboration and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Delta state. The findings from this study are corroborated by a previous study by Shilpi (2017) which revealed that community participation in resource sharing therefore is the creation of opportunities to enable all members of a community and the larger society to actively contribute to and influence in the development process and to share equitably in the fruits of development

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the study have been able to establish the fact that community collaboration contributes to teachers' job performance hence there should be room for community to be fully involved in the activities of the schools. The effective involvement of the community in curriculum implementation will bring about the provision of funds, infrastructural facilities, maintenance of

discipline, decision making process, effective school management and a sense of ownership of the schools by the community itself and all of these will enhance teachers' performance.

Recommendations

Considering the findings, discussion and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The government should allow communities to be involved in the activities of the school by deregulating education.
2. Principals should give room for community collaboration so that the community members can increase their participation in school management.
3. Government should enforce laws, regulations and sanctions that will compel parents and communities to be actively involved in the management of education.

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